

A Holistic Assessment Framework for Evaluating Buildings' Green and Digital Readiness Level

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Abstract— Smart buildings assessment methodologies are important tools utilized across all stages of transitioning towards a greener, smarter, and energy-efficient building sector. Existing assessment methods either focus only on specific building aspects, or consider buildings with particular technical characteristics, or require explicit technical knowledge by the users to evaluate building performance. Consequently, this paper proposes a holistic and flexible assessment framework that encompasses all facets of a building, including green factor, energy efficiency, occupants' comfort, and digitization levels. The proposed framework does not require strong technical knowhow to perform the assessment and can be generally applied for evaluating different buildings by providing basic information about their main characteristics. The assessment framework was applied to a real commercial building, demonstrating its effective use in evaluating overall building performance and analyzing the score in each individual impact category or domain. In addition, two potential action plans were formulated by utilizing the proposed framework to explore different pathways for enhancing the building's performance.

Index Terms—Assessment framework, energy efficiency, green and digital transition, occupant comfort level, smart buildings.

I. INTRODUCTION

The progression of smart buildings is closely linked to the global trend towards greener and more digitized building sectors. This shift aims to enhance the energy performance of structures and promote efficient and sustainable use of resources. Concurrently, integrating automation solutions is essential for improving the convenience and comfort of occupants and for ensuring an effective energy management.

A pivotal and necessary step in the renovation or reconstruction of a building involves employing an assessment methodology to evaluate its readiness level in terms of being smart, green, and digital. These methodologies function as frameworks for appraising the transition of an existing building to a smart configuration, either during or after renovation, as well as for evaluating a building's capabilities during the construction phase [1]. Consequently, the development of such an assessment framework is of critical importance throughout all stages of building renovation or construction and has been extensively studied in recent years [1], [2].

One of the most widely recognized assessment methodologies that has been used by the European Union is the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) [3]. This assessment methodology utilizes a list of buildings' services, which are then divided into different domain groups that are evaluated based on functionality levels. Each functionality level is then evaluated using different assessment criteria. The assessment criteria are categorized in three general categories such as a) energy savings and operation, b) respond to user needs and c) energy flexibility. Finally, an explicit weighting method is used for the calculation of the building score (between 0 and 100%). However, despite the wide usage of SRI approach, different studies indicate that this methodology still requires improvements that are correlated with the addition of energy mathematical indicators [4], and the incorporation of district heating features that are correlated to demand management [5]. In addition, an important limitation of SRI method is that the assessment of a building requires strong technical knowhow of building's explicit systems and equipment that are only known by expert engineers. Therefore, for users without related expertise, it is very complicated and difficult to complete the assessment. Finally, SRI method is primarily focusing on assessing how smart a building is and as a result, key building aspects (e.g., thermal insulation, local renewable resources) that are affecting the green and energy efficiency level of the building have been ignored.

Another widely employed multicriteria building assessment methodology is the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) rating system that has been developed by the US Green Building Council [6]. LEED focuses on seven distinct impact categories: climate change, human health, water resources, biodiversity, material resources, green economy, and community. Each impact category comprises a set of mandatory and optional strategies in which prerequisites are the necessary strategies for system operation, while credits are considered optional [7]. The final score is then calculated by evaluating each credit or prerequisite independently and is used for the publication of a certification. However, this methodology has some limitations that are affecting its reliability and robustness on covering all building aspects. Firstly, according to [8], the scoring system implemented in LEED does not include any scoring limitations associated to important building prerequisites and therefore the user can get a certificate even if these

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prerequisites have very low score. Another limitation of LEED is the adaptability level of the methodology. Due to the fact that LEED has been designed and developed strictly using the US standards, the level of importance of the impact categories and even the structure of the methodology does not easily allow to be adopted and used efficiently and accurately on other geographical regions [9].

Other building assessment frameworks also exist in the literature such as the Interactive tool for Building Automation and Control Auditing (IBACSA) [10], the scoring system methodology for the evaluation of the level of smartness in commercial buildings [11], and the assessment criteria framework for sustainable non-residential buildings in Saudi Arabi [12]. However, all the aforementioned methods have been designed for buildings with specific characteristics, located at specific geographical locations and affected by specific weather conditions. Therefore, they are unable to be used for different building types located at different countries. Moreover, they are solely focus on only one aspect of building, for example the energy sector, not allowing the user to assess holistically the building’s capabilities and performance.

The findings from the literature analysis of the already existing building assessment frameworks indicates that there is a need for a holistic and user-friendly methodology that can assess all the important aspects of buildings with different characteristics and geographical locations. Within this context, the key contribution of this work is the development of a new straight-forward, multi-criteria, and open-source building assessment framework based on a weighting average scoring methodology to calculate a holistic score for each building and to analyze the building performance by focusing on individual impact categories and building domains. The users are asked to provide simple information through an open-source spreadsheet, considering the functionality level for different Services and Characteristics (S&C) related to various building domains (e.g., heating, cooling, electricity, materials, etc.), and then the tool automates the calculation of overall building score and the individual score at each domain or impact category (i.e., energy efficiency, energy resources, occupants comfort level, smart and digital readiness). It should be highlighted that the assessment framework is integrated as a spreadsheet tool that is made openly available [13], while the scoring system configuration can capture a wide range of buildings and can be easily adjusted to different geographical locations. The proposed assessment framework is applied to actual buildings to showcase its effectiveness for evaluating their performance. Moreover, the proposed framework can be used as a useful tool to formulate a set of potential action plans for upgrading a building and evaluate their impact on enhancing the overall building performance, as demonstrated in this paper.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the methodology of the developed assessment framework. Section 3 demonstrates the use of the assessment framework to evaluate the performance of an actual building and to determine and compare potential action plans for upgrading the building. Finally, Section 4 provides conclusions and future work directions.

Figure 1: Structure of the proposed assessment framework.

II. DEVELOPED ASSESMENT FRAMEWORK

A. A Multi-criteria Assesment Framework

A qualitative-based multi-criteria approach is utilized to develop the proposed assessment framework, similar to the SRI approach; however, the services and characteristics, the building domain, and the impact categories have been totally revised to formulate a holistic and straight-forward method where all the important aspects of the building are properly captured.

To comprehensively assess all crucial aspects of a building, four individual impact categories have been specified, based on which the overall building performance is calculated. The impact categories are: (a) energy efficiency, (b) resources utilization, (c) occupants comfort level, and (d) smart/digital readiness level. To calculate the score for each impact category, the functionality level for various services and characteristics for each building domain need to be specified by the users, as briefly described in Figure 1.

More particular, the proposed evaluation framework considers 6 main building domains to described different facets of a building, such as: (i) heating, (ii) domestic hot water (DHW), (iii) cooling, (iv) ventilation, (v) electricity, and (vi) materials/envelope, as indicated in Figure 1. For each domain, a set of specific Services and Characteristics (S&C) have been selected to adequately describe the building configuration, as presented in Table I. These S&C have been carefully determined to holistically cover a wide range of buildings by combining knowledge and services included in SRI [3] and EN15232 standard [14], while incorporating feedback from building automation experts, and building users.

For each of the 31 individual S&C, various qualitative functionality levels have been established. Users, through the related spreadsheet [13], are able to select the functionality level that most accurately describes the building under evaluation. Typically, a higher functionality level indicates a more technologically advanced building system. In example, for the heating generation S&C, the user can select between different functionality levels: electric resistance heating, oil boiler, gas boiler, electric-based heat-pump or air-conditioner, or geothermal-based heat-pump in order to characterize the building. It is important to be mentioned here that not all services and character

TABLE I. SERVICES AND CHARACTERISTICS FOR EACH BUILDING DOMAIN

Heating	Domestic Hot Water	Cooling	Ventilation	Electricity	Materials/envelope
Heat generators	DHW generation	Cooling generators	Supply air flow control	Renewable energy production	Construction materials
Heat distribution	DHW storage	Cooling storage	IEQ reporting	Electric storage	Thermal insulation materials
Thermal energy storage	DHW performance reporting	Room/Zone temperature control	Ventilation performance reporting	Lighting technology	Windows selection
Room/zone temperature control	DHW generators sequencing	Flexibility and grid interaction		Lighting control	Acoustic insulation materials
Flexibility and grid interaction		Cooling performance reporting		Electric vehicle charging	Low-emitting materials
Heating performance reporting				Electricity perform. reporting	Shading and Blinds
				Energy management	

istics have the same number of functionality levels, but it depends on their type, operation, and control. Moreover, to quantify the effect on each impact (I) category, a scale score S_C^{D-I} , e.g., from 0 to 3, is assigned to each functionality level for each domain (D) specific service and characteristic (C). Based on the scale scoring, a more advanced functionality will result in a higher score for an impact category, while a zero score is given to impact categories that may be unaffected by the specific service or characteristic. It is important to mention that the functionality levels are grouped in a way so the user will be able to select the appropriate building configuration in a qualitatively manner, without requiring explicit technical/engineering knowledge to assess the building performance. Energy efficiency classification of key electrical appliances (for heating, cooling and lighting) is partially incorporated as well.

Hence, a crucial step in the assessment methodology is to accurately identify the functionality levels for all services and characteristics using the related spreadsheet [13], based on the primary building configurations. Then, an initial score is automatically assigned for each S&C according to the selected functionality level. Finally, a scoring calculation method (as described in Section II.B) is automatically processed to calculate the score for each individual domain and for each impact category, while an overall score for the building is also provided.

B. Scoring Calculation Method

A weighted average approach is introduced to calculate the building score for each individual domain and impact category and for generating a total score for the building performance.

First, the user identifies the functionality level for each domain specific S&C and a predefined score S_C^{D-I} is assigned, through the related spreadsheet [13]. Then, for calculating the score S^{D-I} of each domain (D) per impact (I) category, the predefined S_C^{D-I} functionality scores are normalized according to the maximum score S_{C-max}^{D-I} for each S&C, according to (1).

$$S^{D-I} = \frac{\sum (S_C^{D-I})}{(\sum S_{C-max}^{D-I})} \quad (1)$$

where S_C^{D-I} is the predefined score for each functionality level (selected by the user) and S_{C-max}^{D-I} is the maximum functionality score for the corresponding characteristic/service (C) in the specific domain (D) for the relevant impact category (I).

The total score per impact category, S^I , is calculated by,

$$S^I = \frac{\sum_D (S^{D-I} \cdot W_{D-I})}{\sum_D W_{D-I}} \quad (2)$$

where W_{D-I} represent the weighting coefficient of each domain (D) per impact (I) category. It should be noted that $\sum_D W_{D-I} = 1$, while W_{D-I} indicates how intensive the contribution of each domain D is to the total score per impact category (I). It should be clarified that these weighting coefficients are specified in [13] considering Eastern-Mediterranean environmental, social, and geographical characteristics, while the coefficients can be adjusted accordingly to capture buildings in different locations.

Similarly, the total score per domain S^D , can be calculated by (3).

$$S^D = \frac{\sum_I (S^{D-I} \cdot W_{D-I})}{\sum_I W_{D-I}} \quad (3)$$

It should be noted that in this case $\sum_I W_{D-I}$ is not necessarily equal to 1.

The building total score (S) is calculated considering a weighted average approach according to (4),

$$S = \frac{\sum_I (S^I \cdot W_I)}{\sum_I W_I} \quad (4)$$

where W_I are the weights of each impact category I, and S^I is the total score per impact category I, as calculated by (2). The weighted scores for each impact category are determined in [13] considering the characteristic of the Mediterranean region. In case those weights need to be adjusted to capture buildings in other geographical locations, then it should be ensured that $\sum_I W_I = 1$.

C. Assessment Framework Integration as an Open Tool

The proposed assessment framework is integrated in a spreadsheet tool, where the user can specify the functionality level for each domain specific S&C in order to evaluate the building performance. The scoring calculation method is also integrated within the spreadsheet and thus, the user can directly calculate the building overall score and the score per domain or impact category. It should be highlighted that the spreadsheet tool integrating the new assessment framework is made openly available in Zenodo repository[13].

III. BUILDING PERFORMANCE ASSESMENT CASE STUDIES

The developed spreadsheet tool integrating the proposed assessment framework is utilized to: (a) evaluate the performance of an actual building according to its initial configuration, and (b) determine possible action plans to effectively upgrade the performance of the specific building.

The commercial building used as offices for the Cyprus Energy Agency (CEA) is used as the building under evaluation for

these case studies. The building is located in Nicosia, Cyprus, and has been structurally renovated in 2019. In its initial configuration (i.e., building state at the beginning of 2023), the building did not include any renewable resources to locally generate its energy needs sustainably and was not equipped with any specific digital or smart solutions for managing building operations. Hence, the proposed building assessment framework is used to evaluate the performance of the initial building configuration (Section III.A) and then to determine possible actions to further upgrade its performance (Section III.B).

A. Performance Evaluation of an Actual Building

To evaluate the performance of the CEA building according to its initial configuration, all the necessary information for the building S&C functionality level has been provided by interviewing CEA personnel. It should be indicated that the personnel providing the requested information did not have any technical or engineering expertise.

By using the proposed methodology, the calculated overall score of the CEA initial building was 33.63% which is quite low and indicates that further improvements and installations required on the building. Furthermore, the calculated individual impact categories scores and domains scores are presented in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. According to the calculated scores of the initial building configuration presented in Figure 2, a medium score (between 40% and 50%) is achieved for the energy efficiency and occupants comfort level impact categories, while a low score is indicated for the resources utilization and smart/digital readiness level. This is justified by (a) the absence of any renewable energy technology that will reduce the energy consumption and the emissions, and (b) the non-integration of any smart system to monitor, manage and control building operations regarding indoor air quality and power consumption. Furthermore, by analyzing the individual domain scores in Figure 3, it can be observed that materials/envelope is relatively high (76%) due to the recent structural renovation of the building, heating domains score is above 40%, while cooling and domestic hot water domains are following with scores between

30%-40%. Ventilation has a low score of 20%, while electricity domain has the lowest score with just 12%.

B. Action Plans to Upgrade Building Performance

As indicated by the total score of the initial building configuration, it is important to take further actions to drastically improve the performance of the building. By analyzing the initial building's scores of the impact categories and domains it was decided that the action plans should mainly focus on: (a) the addition of smart systems for monitoring energy performance and indoor air quality (IAQ) of the building, (b) the installation of renewable energy technologies to sustainably generate a significant portion of the building demand, and (c) the installation of a full automated system for energy management and control. Considering the aforementioned conclusions, two different action plans have been introduced and assessed:

- **Action Plan 1:** Installation of IAQ sensors and power meters, installation of Photovoltaic (PV) panels covering 50-60% of the yearly total energy consumption of the building, and digital integration of the above components on an online platform for live data monitoring and reporting.
- **Action Plan 2:** All actions included in Action Plan 1, plus the addition of: (a) batteries for energy storage, (b) electric vehicle parking and charging points (20% of the total parking area) with online reservation system, and (c) installation of a full automated building management system for flexible and optimized control of the electrical appliances.

By using the proposed assessment framework, the total score calculated for Action Plan 1 is 61.5%, while for Action Plan 2 is 82.1%. Both scores are significantly higher than the initial building score (33.63%), showing that by implementing the proposed actions the performance of the building will be improved. To further investigate how each impact category and domain is affected by the implementation of each action plan, comparisons of the impact categories and building domain scores between the initial case and the two action plans are presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively.

Figure 2: Initial CEA building impact categories scores.

Figure 3: Initial CEA building domain scores.

According to Figure 4, applying Action Plan 1 will result in a significant increase in the scores of smart/digital readiness and occupant comfort level impact categories. This is attributed to the utilization of IAQ sensors and smart meters for monitoring through a digital platform, which not only elevate the building's technological sophistication but also contribute to maintaining or enhancing indoor air quality (IAQ), thus improving occupants' comfort. Additionally, as expected, the installation of the PV panels increased noticeably the score of the energy efficiency and resources utilization impact categories. Moreover, Action Plan 2 results in significant increases in scores across all impact categories, indicating a comprehensive upgrade of the initial building to a green, energy-efficient, and smart standard.

The same observations can be extracted by analysing the domain scores as presented in Figure 5. For Action Plan 1 almost all domains' scores have been increased over than 20%, while for Action Plan 2 the scores of all domains are approximately 40% higher than the initial building. The materials/envelope domain has remained unaffected, since no structural changes have been considered in those actions plans, as the building is recently renovated in terms of thermal insulation.

Figure 4: Comparison of the impact categories scores for initial case (blue), Action Plan 1 (orange), and Action Plan 2 (gray).

Figure 5: Comparison of the domain scores for initial case (blue), Action Plan 1 (orange) and Action Plan 2 (gray).

It is important to mention that each action plan for upgrading the building performance is directly associated with an implementation cost. Therefore, choosing the best action plan should not only be based on the total calculated score, but the decision making should be taken considering both technical and economic perspectives where the investment cost for implementing each action plan should be accounted. Moreover, it should be highlighted that within the GoGreen project, the analysis performed for the CEA office building through the proposed building assessment framework was utilized in the decision-making process for upgrading the specific building. The action plan 1 has been chosen, mainly due to budget restrictions, and the upgrade process was performed within 2023. Hence, the CEA building total score was improved from 33.63% to 61.5% by actually implementing action plan 1, upgrading the building in sustainable, efficient, comfort and intelligent manner.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE POTENTIALS

This work introduces a holistic, user friendly, flexible, and reliable building assessment framework that can be used by technical and non-technical experts to evaluate the overall building performance capturing all the important building domains. The methodology relies on a weighted average scoring systems that analyze various services/characteristics for each building domain and provide a total score for the building performance or individual scores per domain or per impact categories. The new building assessment framework is integrated as a spreadsheet tool which is made openly available to be publicly used. The proposed assessment framework has been used to evaluate the performance of an actual commercial building, while it has also been utilized to formulate an effective action plan to upgrade the performance of the building under evaluation. Through the assessment framework, explicit actions have been included to improve low-scoring services and

characteristics of the initial building and thus, to effectively upgrade the overall building performance.

Some future improvements can contribute towards the wide utilization of the proposed building evaluation framework. Such improvements are: a) inclusion of an estimated implementation cost to improve the functionality level of a specific building's service by considering both technical and economic perspectives on the decision making for upgrading the building performance, and b) adjustment of the weighting coefficients to cover multiple geographical locations and to enable the wide utilization of the proposed assessment framework.

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